
5G EVE

s

5G European Validation platform for Extensive trials

Deliverable D7.7 Report on Training activities after Year 3

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List of Acronyms and Abbreviations

<i>Acronym</i>	<i>Meaning</i>
<i>CNFs</i>	Containerized Network Functions
<i>KPI</i>	Key Performance Indicator
<i>MAC</i>	Medium Access Control
<i>MEC</i>	Multi-access Edge Computing
<i>NFV</i>	Network Function Virtualization
<i>OCP</i>	OpenShift Container Platform
<i>OGR</i>	Officine Grandi Riparazioni
<i>ONAP</i>	Open Network Automation Platform
<i>OPNFV</i>	Open Platform for NFV
<i>ORAN</i>	Open Radio Access Network
<i>PC</i>	Project Coordinator
<i>RAN</i>	Radio Access Network
<i>SME</i>	Small-Medium Enterprise
<i>UCs</i>	Use Cases
<i>WP</i>	Work Package

Executive Summary

This deliverable provides an overview of the training activities in year 3 of 5G EVE as well as plans for passing training activities to selected companion projects making use of 5G-EVE infrastructure. We review the basic objectives for training activities in 5G EVE and then describe the two training events targeting users from companion H2020 ICT-19/22/42/56 projects that occurred in December 2020 and June 2021.

1 Introduction

The training activity in 5G EVE is part of the Training task (T7.3) in the Community Building Work Package (WP7) whose main objective is to provide end-users guided hands-on experience for using the facilities, especially those from partners representing vertical industries within 5G EVE and afterwards from associated projects in the context of ICT-19 and ICT-22 calls. The activity furthermore facilitates the collection of measurements and guides the analysis and dissemination of results derived from them. It also provides several means to train *within* the 5G EVE community, in particular to allow for interoperability between the facilities in different geographic locations and joint experimentation across sites. The actual means for training varies from facility to facility but includes a combination of workshops, tutorials, webinars, online collaborative documentation, community mailing lists and online real-time interactions using tools such as *slack*¹. The most important aspect of real-time tools is that they allow direct interaction with maintainers of the facilities. In order to be effective, the content provided by these methods should be useful and easily accessible. Moreover, the methods should contribute to the sustainability of the facilities beyond the timeframe of the 5G EVE project, in order to foster both academic and international collaboration in industry-driven initiatives such as OPNFV, ORAN and ONAP.

For a more detailed set of objectives of T7.3 please consult D7.5 [1].

We first provide a description of the webinar carried out on the Italian site in November 2020 showcasing the use-cases centered around the “Innovation Mile” in Turin. We then give an overview of the tutorial covering the open-source components used on the French site, in particular ONAP and OpenAirInterface. Finally, we provide information regarding the interactive training activities that were used to assist users during the experimentation phase as well as some current plans for continuing training activities after the project’s lifetime through companion projects.

¹ Slack (www.slack.com) Is an interactive tool for managing teamwork. It is organised in channels providing a single place for messaging, tools and files. It is particular suited for technical interaction.

2 Italian Site Training Webinar

The Italian site training webinar was held on November 18, 2020, showcasing the Use Cases (UC) centered around the “Innovation Mile” in Turin, which is served by the TIM commercial network and is connected to the indoor facilities on the premises of TIM and Politecnico di Torino/ CNIT – National Inter-University Consortium for Telecommunications. In the webinar, three vertical use cases deployed in the Italian site were demonstrated: Smart Transport, Smart City, and Smart Tourism, presenting relevant details of each use case as well as a live demonstration for each of them. The webinar showed the visualization of the metrics collected during the execution of the use cases on the 5G EVE platform as well as an example of how the platform can be used.

2.1 Overview of Content

The webinar had the following Agenda:

- Welcome and introduction
- 5G EVE overview
- Italian site overview
- Use Case 1: Smart Transport
- Use Case 2: Smart City
- Use Case 3: Smart Tourism
- Q&A on 5G EVE Italian site and use cases
- Summary and future plans

The welcome and introduction by the 5G EVE Project Coordinator (PC) had the goal of highlighting the objectives and motivation of the use cases set up by the three internal verticals in 5G EVE, focused on mobility in the urban area. The PC described the methodological framework and technologies, specifically related to data collection and data analysis, with a focus on the results output by each use case.

The vertical KPIs and Network KPIs for each UC were then presented before the description of the test bed and experiment workflow for the execution of experiments.

After a brief overview of the Italian 5G EVE site, Ares2t introduced the Smart Transport UC, explaining the definition of three services powered by 5G EVE to enhance multi-modality between railway network and other collective transportation services:

- *The 5G EVE tracking service* collects and transmits raw data from sensors built-in user’s mobile device (no additional equipment required) to dedicated 5G EVE MEC server.
- *The 5G EVE recognition service* analyses collected data and automatically identifies of passenger mobility patterns and related status (still, walking, running) and transport modalities (car, bus, metro, tram, bike, train).
- *The 5G EVE urban mobility service* collects raw data and identified status and/or modality and transmits enriched information to the OneM2M ICON platform for identifying different transportation modality demands, performing spatial planning and enabling efficient trip planning and control.

The execution of the experiments for the UC and their integration in the 5G EVE portal was then illustrated before a live video feed from the Innovation Mile allowed the audience to see such experiments conducted by 5G EVE personnel on the field.

Next, the Smart City – WiFi Scanner UC was presented, beginning with the explanation of the underlying scientific principles, i.e., that scanners installed in the Innovation Mile passively capture the "probe requests" sent periodically by smartphones to find known APs, using the smartphone’s MAC anonymized address as fingerprint. The online dashboard accessible via the 5G EVE portal and showing flow densities and flow

mobility patterns were then presented to the audience. The description of the onboarding of the UC service blueprint concluded the UC presentation.

Finally, the third UC was introduced: Smart Tourism, i.e., an app for Augmented Reality to enhance the accessibility of cultural sites and explore correlated digital information as well as different types of media (pictures, video, 3D maps) providing additional information to visitors of heritage sites. After showing the procedure to onboard the UC service blueprint, a live broadcast from the Officine Grandi Riparazioni (OGR) on the Innovation Mile introduced the audience to the Augmented Reality app used in the context of an art installation in the courtyard of OGR. At the end of the live broadcast, the KPIs resulting from the live test were shown to the audience.

The webinar was closed by providing an outlook to the further improvements planned for the three Use Cases. The targeted audience was technically inclined users of 5G EVE from ICT-19 and other projects, SMEs, vertical industry actors. The full set of slides are available on the 5G EVE website along with an audio-video recording.

3 French Site “Open-Source” Training Webinar

A one-hour online tutorial was held on June 17, 2021 and provided an overview of the end-to-end open-source components of the French 5G-EVE site. The tutorial was given by representatives of EURECOM and Orange. It began with an overview of the container-based architecture of the computing cluster at EURECOM based on RedHat's OpenShift Container Platform (OCP). It then showed how the cluster will be extended to remote radio sites in Paris and Bucharest Romania in the context of the 5G-VICTORI project. A good part of the discussion dealt with describing the challenges of integrating 5G-EVE's ONAP framework with the OCP cluster. Orange detailed their contributions to the ONAP community related to deployment of containerized network functions (CNFs). EURECOM provided details on preparing 5G Telco CNFs (RAN and Core) under Kubernetes/OCP for automated deployment. This highlighted the work that was done by EURECOM during the course of 5G-EVE for using OpenAirInterface in Kubernetes environments. A live demonstration of the end-to-end open-source solution using the radio infrastructure in Sophia Antipolis was shown. This included both non-standalone (NSA) and standalone (SA) components based on OpenAirInterface.

The event was attended by 29 participants representing technically inclined users of 5G-EVE from ICT-19 and other projects, SMEs, vertical industry actors.

3.1 Overview of Content

- Quick overview of 5G-EVE and the French site
- Physical Infrastructure Used in the tutorial
 - Computing/Switching
 - Sophia Antipolis (OpenShift)
 - Paris
 - Radio
- Telco CNFs and OpenShift Environment
- ONAP Integration
- About services provided in the infrastructure
 - Reasons (i.e. multi-cluster orchestration) How to prepare CNFs for ONAP
- Demo
 - Deployment of openairCN components in Sophia via ONAP from Paris Infrastructure
 - Running 5G RAN in Sophia Antipolis

The slides used in the tutorial are provided in the Appendix.

4 Additional Training Sessions and Related Future Activities

EURECOM provided additional continuous support to its partners via online slack channels and dedicated webinars. This included:

- training for OPNFV partners (Kaloom Networks, RedHat) for replicating the current deployment of OpenAirInterface containerized network functions on OpenShift in Sophia Antipolis on similar infrastructure in Canada. This is an on-going activity now to extend the OPNFV use-case of the Sophia Antipolis infrastructure.
- Training for ICT-19 5G!Drones partners for deploying a vertical service (Airbus software) and using the Sophia Antipolis infrastructure. This involved assistance for building and deploying software on Kubernetes (OCP) and making use of the local service monitoring framework developed by 5G!DRONES partners on the infrastructure. Support will continue in the context of 5G!DRONES after the end of 5G-EVE.
- Support for ICT-19 5G-VICTORI partners on replicating portions of the 5G-EVE Sophia Antipolis Infrastructure at Orange premises in Romania. Support/Training will continue in the context of 5G-VICTORI after the end of 5G-EVE.
- Support for ICT-42 5G-RECORDS partners on replicating 5G-RAN components in their labs for pre integration testing prior to integration on 5G-EVE Sophia Antipolis. Support will continue in the context of 5G-RECORDS after the end of 5G-EVE.
- Continuous support for USA NSF PAWR platforms on replicating 5G RAN/Core components on their platforms. Dedicated slack channels for support/training on OpenAirInterface for Northeastern university, North Carolina State University, University of Utah and Iowa State University.

Additional future training on the 5G-EVE site in Sophia Antipolis will continue after the end of 5G-EVE in the context of the H2020 INFRAI-2020-2 SLICES-SC project [2]. Moreover, EURECOM will ensure continued support of the 5G-EVE infrastructure in the context of the French National project “Engage-5G and Beyond” [3] which will carry on the effort started in 5G-EVE in a national context.

5 Conclusions

This deliverable provided an overview of the training activities in year 3 of 5G EVE. We reviewed the basic objectives for training activities in 5G EVE and then described the two training events targeting users from companion H2020 projects that occurred in December 2020 and June 2021. We then described some specialized training and customized support certain EU and international partners.

Appendix

Slides from the Italian Site Webinar

5G EVE Webinar Italian Site Demo

5G EVE's Italian site

This Project has received funding from the EU Horizon research and Innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 815074

Outline

- **Introduction by Project Coordinator**
- **Webinar overview** by Ares2t
- **Smart Transport – Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis** by Ares2t
 - Presentation of the Use Case
 - On field perspective
 - Metric visualization
- **Smart City – Smart Turin WI-FI Scanner** by CNIT
 - Presentation of the Use Case
 - Experimental results
 - Metric visualization on 5G portal
- **Smart Tourism** by CNIT
 - Presentation of the Use Case
 - On field perspective
 - Experimental results
 - Metric visualization on 5G portal
- **Q&A**

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5G EVE Webinar Italian Site Demo

Webinar overview
Ares2t – Silvia Canale

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Overview

- **Introduction**

- Objectives and motivation
- Methodological framework and technologies
- Vertical KPIs
- Test bed and experiment workflow for the execution of experiments

- **Use Case Presentations**

- Smart Transport – Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis
- Smart City – Smart Turin WI-FI Scanner
- Smart Tourism

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Introduction – Objectives

- Three over six internal verticals in 5G EVE are focused on mobility in urban area

Smart Transport

Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis
(Use Case 1.2)

Goal – Identification of anonymous *mobility patterns* in urban areas by the automatic *recognition of the users' transportation mean* for **traffic management** and **peak prevention** in LPT and Railway Stations

Smart City

Smart Turin WI-FI Scanner
(Use Case 5.1)

Goal – Analysis of anonymous *mobility flows* in urban areas where **safety and security must be monitored**, or when large **crowd gatherings should be detected** (e.g., on-demand public transport)

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Introduction – Objectives

Smart Tourism

5G for enhanced cultural experience
(Use Case 2.1)

Goal – Development of an AR-based app that exploits the support of the 5G network for live interaction and multimedia content access

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Introduction – Motivation

Smart Transport

Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis
(Use Case 1.2)

Motivation – Thanks to 5G mobile communications, it is possible analyzing real time raw data through large scale data analytics to provide added value information for decision making in traffic congestion management

Smart City

Smart Turin WI-Fi Scanner
(Use Case 5.1)

Motivation – Pervasiveness of mobile devices allows to define an “electromagnetic signature” (e.g., active Wi-Fi interface) of each person. Wi-Fi scanners that are distributed across an area allow to identify people mobility flows

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Introduction – Motivation

Smart Tourism

5G for enhanced cultural experience
(Use Case 2.1)

Motivation – Enhancement of the fruition of architectural heritage and support of "intelligent" tourism

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Introduction – Methodological framework and technologies

Smart Transport

Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis
(Use Case 1.2)

Data are collected from *sensors built-in user's mobile device* (no additional equipment required)

Data analysis is performed on 5G MEC server in *distributed way and close to the data source*

The service returns each user the *real time estimated modality* and *publishes mobility patterns* on OneM2M ICON

Smart City

Smart Turin WI-FI Scanner
(Use Case 5.1)

Data are collected from *WiFi scanners connected to the mobile network* (no user involvement required)

Data analysis is performed on 5G MEC server in *distributed way and close to the data source*

The service returns *the number of devices under each scanners* and shows the *mobility flows on a map*

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Introduction – Methodological framework and technologies

Smart Tourism

5G for enhanced cultural experience
(Use Case 2.1)

Data needed by the AR app are fed to mobile users from a 5G MEC server *close to the data source*

The service is thus extremely responsive and the user experience is enhanced

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Introduction – Vertical KPIs

Smart Transport

Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis
(Use Case 1.2)

Vertical (application) KPIs

1. Tracking response time
2. Tracking memory usage
3. Recognition response time
4. Recognition memory usage
5. Recognition accuracy
6. Recognition network time

Smart City

Smart Turin WI-FI Scanner
(Use Case 5.1)

Vertical KPIs

1. CPU usage
2. Memory usage
3. Bandwidth

Network KPIs

- Network availability
- Network latency
- Device density

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Introduction – Vertical KPIs

Smart Tourism

5G for enhanced cultural experience
(Use Case 2.1)

Vertical KPIs

1. CPU usage
2. Memory usage

Network KPIs

- Network latency

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Introduction – Test bed

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Introduction – Experiment Flow Activities

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5G EVE Webinar Italian Site Demo

Smart transport
Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis
Ares2t – Silvia Canale, Alberto Rainieri, Vincenzo Suraci

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Smart Transport – Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis and monitoring

- Three services powered by 5G EVE to enhance multi-modality between railway network and other collective transportation services
 - **5G EVE tracking service** collects and transmits raw data from *sensors built-in user's mobile device* (no additional equipment required) to dedicated 5G EVE MEC server
 - **5G EVE recognition service** analyses collected data and automatically identifies passenger mobility patterns and related status (still, walking, running) and transport modalities (car, bus, metro, tram, bike, train)
 - **5G EVE urban mobility service** collects raw data and identified status and/or modality and transmits enriched information to the OneM2M ICON platform for
 - identifying different transportation modality demands
 - performing spatial planning
 - enabling efficient trip planning and control

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Smart Transport – Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis and monitoring

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Smart Transport – Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis and monitoring

The Use Case is based on design, implementation and integration of three software services:

- 1) **5G EVE Tracking Mobile App** (Android App) is a mobile application used by the end-user for collecting and sending data to the back-end system and communicating the predicted transportation mode
- 2) **5G EVE recognition service**: it is the back-end system which analyses and estimates real time user status and transportation mode through machine learning recognition models
- 3) **5G EVE info mobility service**: it is a software application with the aim of providing aggregated information in terms of mobility flows and patterns of interest based on the OneM2M by TIM

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Execution of experiments – Overview

Experiment – Smart Transport Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis (UC1.2)

The experiment shows real time mobility pattern of each user: trajectory and status or mean of transportation

Two people will use the 5G EVE Tracking Mobile App (Android App) to

- start the data registration session
- indicate their status (still, walking, running)
- get back real time status estimation

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Execution of experiment – E

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Smart Transport – Urban mobility 5G data flows analysis and monitoring

Use Case architecture

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Integration into the 5G EVE portal

Use Case onboarding of the Vertical Service Blueprint

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Integration into the 5G EVE portal

Use Case creation of the Experiment Blueprint

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Visualization of Vertical KPIs

Use Case Vertical KPIs visualization dashboard

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Execution of experiments

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Conclusions 1/2

- Mobility in urban area
 - Smart transport: to identify the status/transportation mean of each person
 - Smart city: to identify the flow of people
 - Complementary approaches
 - *macroscopic vs microscopic* mobility model
- Enhanced Touristic experience
 - Smart tourism: massive download of multimedia content through an AR-based app

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Conclusions 2/2

- 4G vs 5G technologies
 - centralized vs distributed data analysis (MEC)
 - low vs high device density
 - scalable applications
- Many applications
 - Multi/inter modality mobility patterns for Spatial Urban Mobility Planner (SUMP)
 - Mobility monitoring, event identification for public security operators
 - Customer insights for Railway Station Management
 - Valorization and popularization of cultural heritage

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Q&A

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Slides from French Site Open-Source Tutorial

A Tutorial on the Open-Source Tools of the French 5G-EVE Site

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5G-EVE Open-Source Tutorial 17th of June 2021

Agenda

- Quick overview of 5G-EVE and the French site
- Physical Infrastructure Used in this tutorial
 - Computing/Switching
 - Sophia Antipolis (OpenShift)
 - Paris
 - Radio
- Telco CNFs and OpenShift Environment
- ONAP Integration
 - About services provided in the infrastructure
 - Reasons (i.e. multi-cluster orchestration) How to prepare CNFs for ONAP
- Demo
 - Deployment of openairCN components in Sophia Antipolis via ONAP
 - Running RAN in Sophia Antipolis + Paris

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Agenda part 2

- Future steps
 - 5GIDrones use-case : automated-CNF generation/deployment
 - Extension to Romania (5G-VICTORI)
 - Integration of CNF for 5G RAN elements + 5GC

French Site Facility - Concept

Open-Source Dimension

E2E 5G Cloud Native Network
 Heather Kirksey, VP Community & Ecosystem, Linux Foundation
 Ashar Sayeed, Chief Architect, Red Hat
 Fu Qiao, Technical Lead, China Mobile

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Ecosystem Partners

High Level POC Network

End to End Setup

- 5G PoP: KubeCon San Diego, USA
- SG Lab: Kaloomb Montreal, Canada
- Eurescom: Sophia Antipolis, France

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open5GLab k8s cluster

- **6 3/6 Tbit/s switches Tomahawk + Tofino (P4), EdgeCore Networks**
 - 6 for switching fabric
 - 1 additionally for 5G UPF (Kaloomb Networks Edge Fabric)
- **k8s Servers**
 - Worker nodes: 8xDell R640 Xeon Gold 6154/6254 (36 core 3.6 GHz)
 - master nodes : 3x Dell R440 Xeon Silver (20 Core 2.4 GHz)
- **Jumphost**
 - Dell R630 Xeon E5-v4 (20 Core 2.4 GHz)
 - Access to open5GLab network and OCP cluster
- **Service Monitoring**
 - One VM with external access for partners requiring HTTP-based service monitoring and configuration
 - Currently used in 5G-DRONES project
- **Current Interconnections**
 - 1 Gbit => RENATER (Geant)
 - + ssh VPN Tunnel to Orange Labs network (~500 Mbit/s) for control plane and moderate user-plane
 - High-speed to INRIA/RENATER (400 GBps under deployment currently)
- **NFVI is currently RedHat Openshift Container Platform (OCP) 4.4**
 - 200-core full license under RedHat Partner program
- **Bare-Metal Sandbox**
 - Several radio nodes and machines for unitary development/testing
 - Community access

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Physical Infrastructure in Sophia Antipolis

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Physical Infrastructure : left side

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Networking+ Real-Time

- Multiple k8s namespaces/projects sharing cluster and radio resources
 - “oai” namespace, currently has operational EPC and 4G/5G RAN pods used in 5G-EVE/5G-DRONES, etc.
 - “5geve” namespace, ONAP deployed EPC components
 - “5g-drone” namespace, for MEC components (e.g. 5G-DRONES)
 - Developer namespaces
 - oai-ci/cd namespace
 - Jenkins-based CI/CD
 - For deploying testing instances of OAI components (simulation and real-time)
- Pods in different namespaces can access others and bare-metal machines used for specific purposes
 - e.g. HSS / AUSF / UDM can be shared among all namespaces

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Networking + Real Time

- Network topology can be dynamic, being done progressively, primarily in MEC Components
 - => still a lot of manual configuration (e.g. IP addresses and routes, etc.)
- Many pods (e.g. OAI RAN and Core) use Multus CNI for providing multiple interfaces within containers
- Specific networking elements
 - RUs (e.g. AW2S, USRPs, and Benetel) are physical nodes on the cluster network but can be accessed from pods in any namespace. No mechanism yet for “reserving” a radio node.
 - Today AW2S and some USRPs are pooled and accessible from all machines, Benetel is
 - Kaloom UPF + P4-based Edge Fabric is installed on the site
 - Will be used a main switching entity for high-speed access to site
 - To replace “soft” UPF/SPGWu
 - Can connect to several core networks (4G/5G) in parallel
- Some nodes use a Real-time OCP configuration (real-time version of RH Core OS)
 - RAN elements : machines with fronthaul interface
- Machines with HW accelerators
 - GPUs + Xilinx T1 cards
 - offload

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Basic openairinterface-k8s Deployment Architecture

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A bit about the “Telco CNFs”

- All the CNFs are open-source and usually based on OAI and Mosaic5G
 - Community development
 - e.g. oai-magma MME, now a co-development with the Magma Foundation
- Some exceptions
 - Partner CNFs/VNFs for interoperability testing
 - Nokia LTE/SABox 4G/5G cores
 - Accelleran CU (ICT-42 5GRECORDS/AFFORDABLE5G)
 - Cumucore 5GC (ICT-42 5GRECORDS)
 - Testers
 - DS-tester
 - Amarisoft UE

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ONAP integration

CNF Orchestration

The slide shows a timeline of events for CNF Orchestration. At the top, logos for Orange, Huawei, TEMOSUNG, ANSRUTA, and others are displayed. The main slide content includes:

- REQ-341 – CNFO – Next Steppingstones Towards CNF In Production Deployments**
- Speakers: Lukasz Rajewski (Orange), Seshu Kumar M (Huawei)
- Date: 14.10.2020
- Event: OLF NETWORKING Virtual Technical Meeting

Below the slide is a timeline with three starburst markers labeled REQ-182, REQ-341, and REQ-458. The timeline is marked with the locations Frankfurt, Guilin, and Honolulu.

At the bottom left, there is a European Union flag and text: "This Project has received funding from the EU H2020 research and innovation programme under Grant Agreement No 815074". At the bottom right is the SG EVE logo.

5G NSA Setup

The diagram illustrates a 5G NSA Setup architecture. It features the following components and connections:

- External RRU:** B38 RRU AW2S Jaguar (titania) connected to the eNB via eCPRI 10G.
- Internal RRU:** N78 5G RRU (USRP N310) connected to the gNB via UHD 2x10G.
- Core Network:** A cloud containing MME, SPGWc, and SPGWu in the 5gcore namespace, and HSS in the oai namespace.
- Control Plane:** The eNB (monolithic on Phoenix) and gNB (monolithic on mozart) are connected via X2.
- Interfaces:** S1C and S1U interfaces connect the eNB to the core, and S1U connects the gNB to the core.
- Tools and Platforms:** open5glab sandbox, Wireshark, and ONAP are shown as part of the environment.
- Other Elements:** A laptop image and the OPENSIFT logo are also present.

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5G SA Setup

Future Directions

5G VICTORI: Partners: Orange (FR, RO), Eurécom, energy use-cases NO ensured by the presence of common partners between both projects and same persons involved (Marius, Rodolp

- User-plane functionality at remote location
- Small OCP cluster in Romania for SPGWu/eNB/gNB, reuse of NSA 4G core in Sophia

5G!DRONES: Partners: Eurécom, Orange, Drone Use-case –

- Local service framework for deploying security/surveillance applications (Airbus)
- On-the-fly building and deployment of an Edge Service

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ICT42/56/INFRAIA-2020

- **5G-RECORDS** (ICT-42, running until mid-2022)
 - Deployed at EURECOM (Sophia Antipolis)
 - Localized orchestration and experimentation (no 5G-EVE infrastructure beyond Sophia Antipolis)
 - Integration of 3rd part Telco CNFs (5GC, RAN CU) on Eurecom Infrastructure
 - Use-case 1 : URLLC, TSN for remote real-time high-fidelity audio production
- **AFFORDABLE5G** (ICT-42, running until mid-2022)
 - Deployed at EURECOM (Sophia Antipolis)
 - Localized orchestration and experimentation (no 5G-EVE infrastructure beyond Sophia Antipolis)
 - Low-cost / open-source solutions for 5G
 - Integration of O-RAN RIC elements, CU/DU split, multi-vendor solutions for RAN/Core
- **IntelloT** (ICT-56, running until 2023)
 - Next generation IoT paradigms / convergence between 3GPP and non-3GPP solutions
 - Cyberphysical systems for factories and farming
 - URLLC/TSN for remote control of robotic systems
- **SLICES-RI –Pan-European Research Infrastructure**
 - SLICES = “Scientific LargeScale Infrastructure for Computing/Communication Experimental Studies”
 - SLICES-SC (Starting Community) H2020 running now, more projects to follow
 - Community-driven experimentation in computing/communications

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Conclusions

- Showed an overview of the open-source / open-blueprint components of the French component of 5G-EVE infrastructure
- Integration of ONAP cluster orchestration for CNFs running under RedHat OpenShift Container Platform (OCP)
- Demonstration of live deployment of 3 Core Network CNFs
- Example architecture and demonstration of 5G NSA and SA RAN on the site
- Future and ongoing directions using the infrastructure

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5G EVE

THANK YOU

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